

**GRADUAL SEMANTICS AND THE GRADUAL FUNCTION OF AN
ADVERB
JUST**

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Abstract

The principle of word-by-word description offers wide possibilities for using different techniques, including the most modern ones, as well as the possibility of expanding aspects of individualized characteristics, even pragmatic ones. Work in this direction gives access to a general theory of systemic relations between language units, both lexical and grammatical. A comprehensive understanding of the possibilities of functioning of a single word helps to more accurately imagine the existing system of parts of speech and see the trends operating in it.

Key words: productivity, JUST, predicate, gradual function of adverbs

The productivity of qualitative adverbs “testifies to the growing need for qualitative differentiation of shades of action” [Vinogradov, 1972, P.35]. The adverb under study is simply characterized by its fairly frequent occurrence in speech (20% of all cases studied). The shades in the lexical meanings of an adverb simply vary depending on the lexical meaning of the verb forms being defined.

The meaning of the adverb under study is “lack of complexity, absence of any effort.” The dictionary entry says “easy, effortless, uncomplicated, not difficult.” The meaning is presented in the following contexts: You see how everything is easily resolved when the truth is told. (B. Vasiliev. Tomorrow there was war) // easily solved = “easy, not difficult”; The master explains the success of his work simply: if there were no family, nothing would happen... (From the newspaper “Komsomolskaya Pravda”) // explains simply = “easy”; What different

sounds! And how easily and simply they coexisted in one endless melody. (L. Yakhnin. Singing tree); He is recognized very easily. Before, when our Khokhryukov traveled quietly, we recognized him by his hands. (A. Chekhov. An awl in a bag); Sometimes they refused to answer questions, sometimes they answered briefly, simply and precisely, as if not for judges, but for statisticians to fill out some special tables. (L. Andreev. The story of the seven hanged men).

This value is a characteristic of the main predicate. Using the following transformations, it can be proven that in the named meaning the adverb has a simple semantic scope of action of the main predicate:

easy to solve - *■ the solution is simple (easy); explain simply explanation simple (easy); getting along is easy —► the process of “getting along” is simple (easy); answer simply -► the answer is simple (easy); easy to recognize —► simple (easy) recognition. The meaning in question is accompanied by the connotation “good” (a positive assessment: “what is easy is always good”). It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that assessment presupposes the presence of an assessing subject, a pragmatic subject.

The range of verbs included in the distribution of the adverb simply, which has one meaning and characterizes the main predicate, is quite wide. These are mainly verbs of action (pluck, dirty, do), behavior (leave, hug, get along, throw (in the meaning of “having left, leave”), the result of mental activity (reason, decide), knowledge (learn, teach), state (perish, calm down), speech (explain, answer, explain, speak), involuntary action (happen, happened,).

For example: Fyodor somehow strangely suddenly calmed down, boldly and simply stepped onto the stage flooded with light. (V. Shukshin. I came to give you freedom); This dry, slender man does not allow one to think that he worked hard and loves to work. When he talks, he doesn't complain, he speaks simply, as if remembering someone else. (M. Gorky. Woman); Varenka made a simple and natural move, like everything she does, a movement between a bow and a squat,

and immediately spoke to the prince... (L. Tolstoy. Anna Karenina); He never thought that this long-awaited event would happen so easily. It seemed to him that he would be tested and tested for a long time. (P. Nilin. Probation period); She was generally calm and reasonable, but then her calmness was explained simply: Rita sent her son to her parents back in May and therefore could save other people's children. (B. Vasiliev. And the dawns here are quiet...).

It is also necessary to note the occasional use of the adverb in the analyzed meaning with the verb of movement: And he was vaguely surprised how earlier, in September, he drove along this street so simply and fearlessly and even wanted to meet someone to bow. (L. Andreev. Governor).

In some utterances, the content implied by the main predicate is expressed simply by a syntactically dependent adverb, i.e.

The adverb under study functions as a first-order predicate (it completes the semantics of the verb included in the same predicate). In this case, the adverb simply adjoins verbs of behavior or involuntary action. Moreover, in some cases the adverb is a characteristic of the subjective actant: After all, the whole question was simple and clear and only concerned the way how I could get a piece of bread... (A. Chekhov. My Life); We find in our sources little information about the conquest of blue eyes, about meeting with them. I believe - because these victories are easy. (A. Herzen. Who is to blame?); Life is very simple. (M. Gorky. My universities). This can be proven by the following transformations: the question was simple -► the question was simple (easy); victories are made simply -► victories are simple (not difficult); life is built simply -► life is simple (easy). However, individual examples prove that, while performing the predicative function itself, the adverb under study does not semantically affect the subject actant, but is only a characteristic of the verb included in the predicate with it: Peter I, for example, wanting to protect the forest from cutting down for shipbuilding, acted simply: he resettled 1,515 households from the coast

overnight. (From the newspaper “Komsomolskaya Pravda”) // Peter 1 acted simply -► Peter I’s act was simple (easy), and not Peter 1 was simple. He was kind and gentle, but he treated women the same way as everyone else - like a dog, rudely and simply. (M. Gorky. My Universities) // his attitude was rude and simple (in the sense of “primitive”) —► the attitude is rude and simple (in the indicated meaning), and he is not rude and simple, because in context he is "kind and gentle".

In the meaning under consideration, an adverb simply has a wide scope: it can semantically affect not only the main predicate, but also its subject (the subject of the main predicate): Ideas are clear, simply formulated and include ways of their implementation and dissemination. (From the newspaper “Komsomolskaya Pravda”) // ideas are simply formulated -> the formulation is simple and the ideas are simple.

The issue was resolved simply, clearly, as it is resolved throughout the world of animals, and in the end, people... (A. Serafimovich. City in the steppe) // the issue was resolved simply -> the solution is simple and the question is simple (easy).

And especially here, of course, the mystery of Pushkin is tempting. Perhaps all these flashes of genius in the history of society can be explained simply? So to speak, a happy combination of genes. (G. Volkov. The World of Pushkin) // flashes of genius are explained simply - the explanation is simple and the “flashes of genius” are simple.

Those who move little feel hungry and eat much more often than those who are active. This is explained simply. Under the influence of physical activity, the secretion of catecholamines increases, which inhibit the appetite center in the brain. (From the magazine “Health”) // this is explained simply -* the explanation is simple and “it” is simple.

In this case, the adverb simply includes in its distribution only verbs that

denote the result of the thought process (to be formulated, to be explained, etc.). For example: An ignoramus talks very simply. (V. Soloukhin. Romantic story) // the analyzed meaning is not accompanied by the above-mentioned connotation of “good”: the reasoning is simple (easy) and the ignoramus is “simple” (in the meaning of “unthinking”). From an assessment point of view, this is bad.

In some uses, being a characteristic of the main predicate, the adverb under study simultaneously characterizes the objective actant of the verb: For a beginning poet, advice regarding rhyme, in my opinion, can be formulated briefly and simply: the rhyme should not be the first one that comes across, lying on the surface. (From the magazine “Koster”) II formulate briefly and simply —► the wording is simple and the advice is simple.

...And most importantly, how can you then survive for 19 hours in icy (5 degrees) water and still wait for rescue? The fleet monitoring service explains this “deadly number” simply: all the fishermen were wearing wetsuits with special thermal insulation. (From the newspaper “Komsomolskaya Pravda”) // the explanation is simple (easy) and the “deadly number” is simple (easy, understandable).

The meaning “directly, frankly, bluntly” is realized in the following contexts: I looked out the window: two people were sitting and talking. It's so simple, frankly. (From the newspaper “Komsomolskaya Pravda”); I ask my friend: what is this being done? He, of course, explains simply: “Robbery, and robbers must be beaten like wolves.” (M. Gorky. The Birth of Man); Why do they hate Milosevic so much now? Two years ago, when NATO bombed the city, it was considered almost a symbol of resistance. “He was too rich, and we were too poor,” the middle-aged waitress in the pub next to the broken boutique simply answered. (From the newspaper “Komsomolskaya Pravda”).

The adverb simply, used in this meaning, can be characterized as a determiner of the main predicate:

talk simply (frankly) —► talk simply (frankly);

speak simply -► speech is simple (open); answer simply (frankly) -> answer simply (frankly); explain simply (frankly) —► the explanation is simple (frank).

However, in some uses, the adverb in this meaning is focused on an internal object (i.e. one that is not expressed syntactically) and is correlated with the definition of an object expressed by an adjective: They smacked their tongue, laughed and said contemptuously and simply: “Tu... tu ... that... of course, fools, is it possible in this weather? It is known - Russians. (A. Kuprin); If I’m not a burden to you, I’ll be very glad,” he said simply. (A. Kuprin. Pit); “I can guess where this is all going,” Vera told me, “better just tell me now that you love her.” (M. Lermontov. Hero of our time); And why do you sneak up like a thief, slander, deceive, and be a hypocrite? I would simply say: “I need your life,” and I would give it up without complaint... (A. Bestuzhev-Marlinsky. Ammalat-Bek) II say simply (frankly) -* say in simple (frank) words.

This meaning is realized only in combination with verbs of speech: say, talk, tell, answer, add, explain. However, there are cases of occasional use of the analyzed adverb adjacent to verbs denoting general perception (believe) and purposeful action (hug, remove): And he blessed God, because he believed in him solemnly and simply: as a priest and as a person with a kind soul. (L. Andreev. Life of Vasily Fiveysky); They all spoke in hoarse, harsh voices, scolded, hugged men as simply as if they were all alone on the boulevard... (L. Andreev. Petka at the house in the country).

He simply and impolitely deleted it:

-Well, okay, go ahead. I want to be alone. You have your own rooms, and I don’t let you go. (L. Andreev. Governor).

In the first use, the adverb simply acquires the additional connotation of “without thinking, without explanation,” in the 2nd and 3rd contexts - “without hesitation.”

The meaning in question can be accompanied by both positive and negative connotations: what is explicit does not always leave a good impression. Thus, the adverb simply and in this meaning has a pragmatic orientation (both positive and negative): the assessment comes from the pragmatic subject.

The most common are constructions in which the adverb is simply extended by a high-degree gradator with the adverb very, which denotes a high intensity of manifestation of the attribute. Stylistically, these phrases are neutral and are not accompanied by additional expressive characteristics: Among the panicles of mountain reeds, already completely yellowed, she found low grass, completely invisible to us in the yellow pasture, and spent her time very simply... (M. Prishvin. Ginseng); The look of a person accustomed to interrogation could very easily frighten (A. Romov. Don't shoot at strangers).

Quite rarely there are constructions in which the adverb simply attaches the graders unusually, unusually, unusually, etc. Thus, the speaker denotes a degree of manifestation of a characteristic that exceeds the usual amount. These combinations contain in their meaning the element "extraordinary degree", the presence of which simultaneously implies the presence of the attribute "great degree". Consequently, both of these elements bring into the context a complex, gradual meaning of "extraordinary and great degree": She always has her own opinion and expresses it in an unusually simple way. (E. Sorokin. Continuation of the feat); She put the bag under her arm and, giving him her hand, said unusually simply: "They did everything: they washed it, and they did the rituals. She's still very young with you, if only she could live and live..." (K. Simonov. The Living and the Dead).

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